

Language Acquisition and Learning

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Abstract:

The present paper deals with the concept of language acquisition and language learning, both these things are important for a language learner. Language can either be acquired or learnt. To learn a language means to acquire a language. Language acquisition is the process of building the ability to understand a language, using it to communicate with others

Introduction:

Human beings are different from other animals in the sense that they can speak and understand language. Language is specific for human beings. It is the major medium of expressing thoughts and emotions so human beings need to learn a language. The progress of mankind will be blocked without language. The way of expressing our thoughts or letting others know what is in our minds, what we are thinking about or what we desire, is what we call 'speech' or 'language'. But the question arises, how one associates the meaning of the 'language' or to make it clear, how one learns a language, so it is necessary to see the process of language learning. In which we have to study the process of language acquisition and language learning.

According to O. Jespersen, "Language is a set of human habits, the purpose of which is to give expression to thoughts and feelings". (Aslam 12).

In the words of Bloch and Trager, "A language is a system of arbitrary vocal symbols by means of which a social group co-operates." (Bist 01).

Noam Chomsky in Syntactic Structures defines: "A language is a set (finite or infinite) of

sentences, each finite in length and constructed out of a finite set of elements". (Salim 02).

In other word, we can say that language is the flesh and blood of our culture. We can't imagine a word without language. There will be little communication among the people except by signs and gestures without language. The progress of mankind will be blocked without language.

Language can either be acquired or learnt. To learn a language means to acquire a language. Language acquisition is the process of building the ability to understand a language, using it to communicate with others. It's the process of going from a wordless wonder into somebody who can't stop talking during class.

Language is learned in informal and formal situations. In an informal situation is one when language is not taught, means in this situation language is not learnt for grammar but it is learnt for communication. The first language or mother tongue is learned in an informal situation. A growing child learns language functionally to express himself or herself. Thus by using language the child develops language skills. But in formal situation of language learning it is quite different from the informal one.

The first language is learnt in an informal situation, while the second language is learnt or taught in a formal situation. In other words, mother tongue is acquired, while the second language is learnt. So the two processes are different from each other.

Difference between Acquisition and Learning:

The process of language acquisition and language learning is different from each other. Acquisition of mother tongue is an easy and natural process, learning mother tongue or to acquire first language is quite easy process because from the birth of the child, he is surrounded by the atmosphere where the mother tongue is spoken, so the child gets the utterance quite naturally and easily. On the other hand, learning a foreign language or learning a second language is difficult and artificial process. So, while a teacher teaches in a school, there is such difficult atmosphere in school, and colleges and so it becomes difficult to get. On the contrary mother tongue or first language becomes easy and natural process to learn.

Another difference is that when a child acquires his mother tongue or first language his brain is a clean slate, but when he tries to learn the second language his mind has already captured a language that is his mother tongue. So, he always tries to compare his first language to the second one.

Many times, the first language acquisition helps to learn the second language, but sometime it also hinders the second language. While learning the second language, a child always tries to compare it with first language and makes his task easy. but sometimes his mother tongue does not have the items of the second language correctly and easily.

For Ex.- The word ' Table' helps him to understand both in Marathi and Hindi, and

English too. But the word ' aspiration' in English may create problem for Marathi/Hindi student.

The first language acquisition is inevitable for a child. He must learn this language, because he has no option, whenever he wants to express his desires, he must use this language. On the other hand, second language learning depends on the capability of his mind, as well as it depends on his will power too.

For Ex. - Our children learn the mother tongue like Marathi/ Hindi/ Urdu easily, but as compare it, after 10 years education also they are not found themselves comfortable in English.

Another difference is that the child has unlimited time to acquire his mother tongue. On the other hand, he has limited time for learning a foreign language. Because at home he is free to speak, to use the language with anyone, but in the school, he has to face some restrictions and for second language learning he gets hardly one lecture of 35 to 45 minutes out of 24 hours of a day. In this one hour he tries to complete and learn each and every thing related to a new language, but it also depends on the whims of that teacher, who teaches him the foreign language.

There are many teachers to teach mother tongue like parents, brothers, sisters, friends, etc. But for the second language teaching there is only a classroom teacher to teach the foreign language. It is said that a mother is the first teacher of any child who helps him/ her to acquire the mother tongue easily.

Another and a prominent difference between these two things is that first language acquisition is possible in free and informal situation. There is not any rule and regulation; there is not any fixed time, to learn this language. So the child can learn this language in free environment, with his family members. But on the other hand, for second language learning, the child has to face some rules and regulations,

he has to complete such things in stipulated time; these all things create some restrictions for him. So, to learn a second language becomes a boredom matter for him.

How to acquire the second language:

1. Teacher should create an atmosphere and motivates the learners to learn the language.
2. Teacher should follow the natural order of listening, speaking, reading, writing in his classroom.
3. Only to complete the syllabus should not be the goal of a teacher. He should give the thorough knowledge of language.
4. Teacher should not give much stress on the accuracy in speaking, reading, writing at the beginning. He should expect the correct spells, correct grammar, from the learner in beginning. He must motivate them, and should attract them toward his teaching.
5. A teacher should introduce different kinds of language games, through which he can attract them.
6. Teacher should insist them to use second language in their daily communication.
7. Parent should learn the second language first, after then they can teach them, and will create an atmosphere in which their child can grasp the lectures of free education.
8. Teachers and parents should use the

different audio-visual aids to attract and teach their children.

9. Teacher should insist their student to read English newspapers, to listen English news on Radio, or Television.

Conclusion:

Thus, the first language acquisition and the second language learning are the two important terms in the field of language learning process. Both these processes are similar as well as different. The first language knowledge helps the learner to learn the second language and it also interferes in his learning of the second language.

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